

STUDIES CONCERNING THE AGROSILVOPASTORAL SYSTEM WITH BEECH FROM THE ORIENTAL CARPATHIANS

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Abstract

*The agrosilvopastoral systems specific to the Mediterranean countries with warm and dry climate are also found in our country - from the plain to the mountain area, with permanent settlements. After deforestation, aimed to expand the pasture area which serves as the main source of forage for domestic animal breeding, isolated trees were left, especially to provide shade. The originality of this paper stands in describing an agrosilvopastoral system like this with beech (*Fagus sylvatica*), located in Obârșia - Dulcea from Gurghiului Mountains (on 1.150 m altitude), owned by a compossessorate from Ibănești commune, Mureș County. Pastures found in open field dominated by *Nardus stricta* recorded a pastoral value (PV) of 38,6 % and a green forage production (GM) of 6 t/ha (very poor), with reduced crude protein content (CP) of 11%. The vegetation cover found under beech dominated by *Festuca rubra* and *Poa pratensis* recorded increases in PV with 50% and in GM yield with 60% and a better CP content with 8% compared to the values recorded on pasture without trees. Furthermore, besides proving shade for animals, beech also deliver fruits (beech nut) which serve as food supply for pigs and occasionally for sheep. Considering the higher productivity of pastures found under beech, the well-being of animals, and the biodiversity and not at last the pastoral landscape, we recommend the adoption of a proper management aiming to maintain and conserve the isolated beech located in mountain pastures, taking into account also the climate global warming.*

Keywords: *agrosilvopastoral system with beech, pasture productivity, biodiversity, animal well-being*

INTRODUCTION

Agrosilvopastoral systems are specific to countries with dry climate located around the Mediterranean Sea, known also as "dehesa" and "montado" in Spain and Portugal (OLEA, SAN-MIGUEL 2006). These systems are also found in dry areas from Oregon State (USA) under the name of "Agroforestry" (SHARROW 1994). In our country the combination pasture-isolated trees is known as "dumbravă" or "crâng" resulting from trees excluded from deforestation or after planting, in order to provide shade for animals during the grazing season.

The isolated trees found in pastures hold a well-defined role for mountain area through the shade provided by them, the well-being of animals, scratchers role etc as well as thanks to their role in protecting the vegetation carpet from sun, excess moisture and other benefits (MARUȘCA 2017). These trees serve also as shelters for animals and birds which feed themselves with forage grasses pests. Not at last, a pastoral landscape with trees is more attractive than one without them. This paper provides a first evaluation on the productivity of pastures with beech compared to a pasture without trees.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The investigations were performed in the summer of 2020 on Obârșia Dulcea pasture, located at 1150 m altitude, belonging to the compossessorate from Ibănești commune, Mureș County. This pasture is surrounded by beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) and includes isolated trees aiming to provide shade for animals. The floristic studies were made under trees canopy and in open field without trees on a surface of 100 m². Pasture productivity was made based on these surveys, after a new method (MARUȘCA 2019). Soil samples were collected with a probe on 10 cm depth - from the surface found in the halfway between the stem and the edge of the canopy, in a circle, and also in open field on the diagonal of the square where floristic surveys were performed (10 x 10 m). Grass samples were collected for chemical analysis in order to assess forage quality from both pastures (under trees and from the surface of the floristic surveys). Soil and grass samples were analyzed by specialized laboratories after the usual methods

REZULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results concerning soil agrochemical content are presented first as they have a direct influence on pasture productivity (Table 1).

Table 1

The agrochemical values of soil found in pastures from open field and under beech (Fagus sylvatica)

Specification	UM	1. Open field	2. Under the trees	Dif. 2-1 +, -	%
pH in H ₂ O	ind.	4,7	4,8	+0,1	102
Humus	%	12,12	12,18	+0,06	101
Nitrogen index	%	4,63	4,69	+0,06	101
Mobile phosphorous	ppm	4,0	4,0	0	100
Mobile potassium	ppm	364	> 400	> 36	> 110
Sum of total exchangeable bases (SB)	me/100g	15,1	15,5	+0,4	103
Hydrolytic acidity (Ah)	me/100g	24,4	24,8	+0,4	102
Cationic exchange capacity (T)	me/100g	39,5	40,3	+0,8	102
Degree of saturation in bases (V%)	%	38,2	38,5	+0,3	101
Exchangeable aluminum	me/100g	3,595	3,621	+0,026	101

Generally soils showed a higher acidity (pH 4,7-4,8), high humus content, poor phosphorus content, high potassium and exchangeable aluminum content (3,6 me/100 g sol), being harmful for animal breeding. Under beech, thanks to the animals which sit under their shade, large amounts of organic fertilizers accumulates increasing soil trophicity and impacting the vegetation carpet's quality. Thus, the main soil indicators (pH, V% and humus) increased with 1-2% under trees compared to open field, and potassium content grows over 10%. These changes in soil composition, together with threes shade, improved the floristic composition of the pastures (Table 2).

Table 2

Floristic composition and productivity of pasture found in open field, lighted (L) and under beech, shady (U) located at Ibănești, Mureș County, 1.150 m altitude

Species	Presence (class)		Participation %			%	Indices	
	L	U	L	U	Dif. + -		F	M
Coverage	x	x	100.0	91.7	-8.3	92	x	x
Poaceae								
<i>Festuca rubra</i>	V	V	22.1	31.6	+9.4	143	7	6
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	V	V	16.3	12.0	-4.3	74	7	5
<i>Deschampsia caespitosa</i>	V	V	2.1	3.1	+1.0	147	3	0
<i>Nardus stricta</i>	V	III	43.4	2.7	-40.7	6	3	0
<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>	V	-	1.0	-	x	x	5	3
<i>Calamagrostis epigeios</i>	I	-	1.0	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Poa pratensis</i>	-	IV	-	14.0	x	x	8	6
<i>Poa annua</i>	-	III	-	5.7	x	x	7	2
<i>Poa chaxii</i>	-	I	-	0.7	x	x	7	7
Fabaceae								
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	III	III	3.7	6.3	+2.6	169	8	5
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	III	-	0.4	0.0	-0.4	0	8	6
<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	I	I	0.1	0.1	0.0	100	8	7
Other families								
<i>Thymus montanus</i>	III	I	1.0	0.1	-0.9	14	4	2
<i>Veronica chamaedrys</i>	III	V	0.7	1.4	+0.7	200	4	2
<i>Campanula patula</i>	II	II	0.3	0.3	0.0	100	3	0
<i>Alchemilla vulgaris</i>	I	I	0.3	0.1	-0.1	50	6	4
<i>Prunella vulgaris</i>	V	-	1.3	0.0	x	x	4	2
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	III	-	3.0	0.0	x	x	6	4
<i>Hieracium pilosella</i>	III	-	0.6	0.0	x	x	4	1
<i>Luzula campestris</i>	III	-	0.4	0.0	x	x	4	2
<i>Stellaria graminea</i>	III	-	0.4	0.0	x	x	1	0
<i>Potentilla reptans</i>	II	-	0.4	0.0	x	x	3	0
<i>Carduus acanthoides</i>	I	-	0.4	0.0	x	x	3	0
<i>Carum carvi</i>	I	-	0.1	0.0	x	x	6	3
<i>Galium verum</i>	I	-	0.3	0.0	x	x	5	4
<i>Lycopodium clavatum</i>	I	-	0.3	0.0	x	x	3	0
<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	I	-	0.1	0.0	x	x	7	3
<i>Glechoma hederacea</i>	-	III	0.0	2.1	x	x	3	0
<i>Leontodon autumnale</i>	-	II	0.0	0.3	x	x	5	3
<i>Oxalis acetosella</i>	-	II	0.0	0.4	x	x	3	0
<i>Stellaria media</i>	-	II	0.0	1.9	x	x	1	0
<i>Urtica dioica</i>	-	II	0.0	2.1	x	x	3	0
<i>Euphorbia amygdaloides</i>	-	I	0.0	0.1	x	x	1	0
<i>Fagus sylvatica (juv)</i>	-	I	0.0	6.3	x	x	3	0
<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	-	I	0.0	0.1	x	x	3	0

Continuation Table 2

Total species (no.)	24	21	-3	88	x	x
From which: - forage	16	11	-5	69	x	x
- not forage	8	10	+2	125	x	x
Participation of forage species	52.6	72.4	+19.8	138	x	x
Participation of harmful species	47.4	19.3	-28.4	41	x	x

Gaps in vegetation	0.0	8.3	+8.3	x	x	x
Pastoral value (PV)	38.6	58.0	+19.4	150	x	x
Index for useful phytomass (IM)	2.62	3.87	+1.25	148	x	x
Forage production (GM t/ha)	6.03	9.67	+3.64	160	x	x

Therefore the dominant specie *Nardus stricta* (43%) found in pastures from open field decreased her percentage of participation in the vegetation cover under 3% under shade while valuable species like *Festuca rubra* increased their share from 22% to 32% and *Trifolium repens* with 3%. Furthermore, on pastures located under trees shade species like *Poa pratensis* (14%) and *Poa annua* (6%) appeared. These species with high forage value are not found in pastures located in open field, without trees' shade.

Generally, the valuable forage species share over 70% from the vegetation cover in pastures found under trees and 50% in pastures found in open filed, a participation with 20% more reduced. The quality indicator - pastoral value for the vegetation cover under trees reached 58 and 39 in open field, value reduced with 33%. Forage production under trees (9,7 t/ha) is higher compared to open field (6t/ha) an increase with 60%. The final aim of our study was to assess the differences among the quality indicators determined in laboratory (Table 3).

Table 3

Differences among the quality chemical parameters recorded by sward found in open field pasture (L) compared to sward under trees (U) from Ibănești

Chemical parameters for forage quality assessment	Content %			%
	L	U	Dif. + -	
Crude protein-CP	11,1	11,9	0,9	108
Ash-ASH	8,2	8,7	0,5	107
Crude fiber-CF	37,1	37,6	0,5	101
ADF	41,1	40,8	-0,3	99
ADL	5,1	4,2	-0,8	83
NDF	66,5	67,0	0,4	101
Digestibility-DDM	47,7	49,6	1,9	104
Digestibility-DOM	45,0	47,3	2,3	105

Generally, the nutritive value of the forage resulted from mountain grasslands from beech floor is lower, with crude protein content (CP) over 11% and reduced digestibility of organic matter (DDM). Anyway, the CP and DDM are higher with 4-8% in pastures found under trees compared to those from open field.

All the studied indicators revealed the superiority of the vegetation cover with trees from the agrosilvopastoral system analyzed, compared to that without trees. To these the well-being of animals thanks to trees shade and the beauty of the landscape, difficult to assess, are added.

CONCLUSIONS

The pastures with beech found in agrosilvopastoral systems are superior to those without trees (from productivity, protection and esthetically point of view);

Increases in pastoral value with 50% and in forage productivity with 60% were recorded in pastures under beech compared to those found in pastures without trees;

The comfort and well-being of animals under trees, the higher productivity and, not at last, the agrosilvopastoral landscape esthetic, recommend themselves for their conservation and future promotion.

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